

Sannō Ichijitsu Shintō

also known as “Tōshōgū Faith”, “Tōshō Daigongen Faith”

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Entry tags: Japonic, Kami worship, Religious Group, Shintō, Japanese Buddhism, East Asian Buddhism, Buddhist Traditions, Ancestral Worship, Language, English, Japanese Religions

Sannō Ichijitsu Shinto (山王一実神道) is a religious system developed by the Tendai monk, Nankōbō Tenkai (南光坊天海 1536-1643), to enshrine and worship the founder of the Tokugawa regime (1603-1868), Tokugawa Ieyasu (徳川家康 1543-1616). The imperial court bestowed Ieyasu with the sacred name of Tōshō Daigongen (東照大権現), meaning Great Avatar of Eastern Illumination. The geographical center of Sannō Ichijitsu Shinto was the Tōshō shrine in Nikkō, although satellite shrines would quickly spread throughout the archipelago eventually numbering over five hundred. The sect was overtly political and legitimated the nascent Tokugawa clan by providing a sacred basis for Tokugawa authority. Sannō Ichijitsu Shinto drew from the Tendai sect's Sannō Shinto (山王神道) syncretic Shinto-Buddhist system as a template but replaced Sannō Shinto's deity triad of Ōmiya (大宮), Ni-no-miya (二宮), and Sanshinshi (三真子) with Tōshō Daigongen, Sannō Gongen, and Matarajin (摩多羅神). Sannō Ichijitsu Shinto was initially a highly exclusive cult open only to Ieyasu's blood relatives, high-ranking vassals, and select clergy. This would change as the shrines spread and their attendant rituals and rites gave way to festivals. Non-elites, most often townspeople, became increasingly active in these festivals and by the end of the Tokugawa period, many of the festivals were entirely the province of commoners. These festivals often became grand annual events with some (e.g.: Wakayama Tōshōgū Festival) becoming for a time the largest festival on the archipelago. Although these festivals are still celebrated today, Sannō Ichijitsu Shinto as formulated by Tenkai ceased to exist after the early Meiji separation of Shinto and Buddhism (ca. 1868). At this point, the Buddhist administrative temples (本地堂) of all the Tōshōgū shrines were destroyed or stripped of directorial authority and the Tōshōgū shrines were reappointed as strictly Shinto sites. Regalia that alluded to the syncretic nature of early modern Sannō Ichijitsu Shinto such as portable shrines were moved to other temples or assigned new deities to ensure the strict separation of Buddhism and Shinto. Today, the central shrine at Nikkō boasts over one million visitors each year.

Date Range: 1617 CE - 1868 CE

Region: Japan

Region tags: Japan, East Asia, Asia

Northeast Asia, imperial rival of Tsarist Russia

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Sugahara, Shinkai. “The Distinctive Features of Sannō Ichijitsu Shinto.” *Japanese Journal of Religious Studies* 23, no. 1/2 (April 1, 1996): 61-84.
- Source 2: Boot, W. J. “The Death of a Shogun: Deification in Early Modern Japan.” In *Shinto in History*:

Ways of the Kami, edited by John Breen and Mark Teeuwen. Honolulu, HI: U of Hawaii P, 2000.

– Source 3: Sugahara, Shinkai. Sannō Shintō no Kenkyū. Tōkyō: Shunjūsha, 1992.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: <https://www.britannica.com/topic/Sanno-Ichijitsu-Shinto>

– Source 1 Description: Britannica, T. Editors of Encyclopaedia. "Sannō Ichijitsu Shintō." Encyclopedia Britannica, January 30, 2022.

– Source 2 URL: <http://www.philtar.ac.uk/encyclopedia/shinto/sanno.html>

– Source 2 Description: Overview Of World Religions. Division of Religion and Philosophy University of Cumbria.

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

– Source 1 URL: Tenkai. Tōshōsha engi. Art reproduction. Tōkyō: Shinbi Shoin, 4.
<https://searchworks.stanford.edu/view/11456699>

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– Yes

Notes: Sannō Ichijitsu Shinto was founded as a reaction to the emergent Sōgen Yuiitsu Shinto of the Yoshida clan. Tokugawa Ieyasu was initially deified according to Yoshida Shinto rites just as the preceding hegemon, Toyotomi Hideyoshi (1537-1598), had been. Because the Yoshida inverted the conventional understanding at the time which placed the native kami deities in a subordinate position to the Buddhas, Tenkai challenged Ieyasu's first deification and was able to exhume his remains and rebury and re-deify Ieyasu using Sannō Ichijitsu Shinto rites.

Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Notes: Although Sannō Ichijitsu Shinto was founded through competition between Tendai's syncretic beliefs and the Yoshida school of Shinto, those who worshiped Tōshō Daigongen (Ieyasu) were members of various schools of Buddhism while also practicing a variety of Shinto faiths depending on place of birth and station in life.

Is the cultural contact neutral:

– Yes

↳ Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

↳ Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– Yes

Notes: Initially, the majority of those allowed to worship in the exclusive sacred spaces of the Tōshō Shrines were blood relatives of Tokugawa Ieyasu. The next group allowed restricted access was comprised of high level retainers who had proven themselves loyal to Ieyasu during his life.

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– No

↳ Assigned by class:

– Yes

Notes: Initially, adherents of Sannō Ichijitsu Shinto were members of the bushi (warrior) class. Rites and rituals were presided over by Tendai priests who had been initiated into Sannō Ichijitsu Shinto. This would gradually change over the course of the Tokugawa period (1603-1868) as well-to-do commoners began to infiltrate the previously exclusive sacred spaces dedicated to the deified Ieyasu. This was especially true of the satellite Tōshō Shrines, although the central shrine in Nikkō drew around 30,000 commoner pilgrims a year.

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– No

↳ Assigned by gender:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– No

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– No

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

↳ Are the priests paid by polity:

– Yes

Notes: Tōshō Shrines were often granted lands and taxation rights to support their upkeep and provide for the clergy. In more urban settings, direct stipends and monetary donations were made directly by the ruling elite to priests or institutions.

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

↳ Are the head of the polity and the head of the religion the same figure:

– No

Notes: The head of the Sannō Ichijitsu Shinto faith was initially Nankōbō Tenkai. Subsequently, his disciples took this role. Finally, the position shifted to Rinnōji no Miya Monzeki imperial princes who resided between Nikkō and Edo.

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– Yes

Notes: While irregular, vassals of high-ranking warriors including the shogun would be required to travel in large retinues to pay homage at Nikkō and other sites.

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– No

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Field doesn't know

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (seen as being part of a related larger religious group)

Notes: Sannō Ichijitsu Shinto began under the direct administration of the Buddhist Tendai sect, of which Tenkai was the head. However, as Tendai changed both theologically and administratively over the Tokugawa period, head priests of Tōshō Shrines came to have more independence. This was largely due to the waxing and waning of the Sannō Ichijitsu Shinto faith's popularity with the different Tokugawa shoguns as well as regional lords.

Are there recognized leaders in the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among these leaders:

– Yes

↳ A single leader of a local community:

– No

↳ Multiple religious communities each with its own leader, no hierarchy among these leaders:

– No

↳ "Regional" leaders who oversee one or more local leader(s) (e.g. bishops):

– Yes

↳ A single leader for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– Yes

Notes: Since its inception in 1617 and through the seventeenth century, Sannō Ichijitsu Shinto was controlled by a lineage directly tied to Nankōbō Tenkai. The opening of new shrines required permission and rituals to be carried out by the center (Nikkō). This administrative and theological control would shift in the eighteenth and nineteenth centuries to Rinnōji no Miya, a subset of the Monzeki priests who were descended from the imperial family.

↳ A council or group of leaders for the religious group that oversees all other leaders in the sample region:

– No

↳ Estimate how many levels there are in the hierarchy of religious leadership:

– I don't know

Notes: The hierarchy of the leadership within Sannō Ichijitsu Shinto mirrored that of the Tendai sect. As the Tendai hierarchy changed, so too did that of Sannō Ichijitsu Shinto.

↳ Are leaders believed to possess supernatural powers or qualities:

– No

↳ Are religious leaders chosen:

– Yes

↳ A leader chooses his/her own replacement:

– Yes

↳ Are leaders considered fallible:

– I don't know

↳ Are close followers or disciples of a religious leader required to obediently and unquestionably accept the leader's pronouncements on all matters:

– No

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also "oral scriptures" (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Notes: The canonical work describing Sannō Ichijitsu Shinto is the Tōshōsha Engi (1636). Far more widely spread was a rewritten version called the Tōshō Daigongen Engi (1640). Both of these sets of scrolls were composed by Tenkai. The former was written in literary Chinese and was a traditional engi concerned with the establishment and development of the Sannō

Ichijitsu Shinto faith and its attendant shrines. The latter was written in combined Japanese and Chinese characters, penned by numerous members of the court including the retired Emperor, Go-Mizuno (1596-1680). It was also richly illustrated by Kanō Tan'yū (1602-1674). Replicas were made and distributed to numerous Tōshō Shrines.

↳ Are they oral:

– Yes

Notes: There was a deep oral tradition within Sannō Ichijitsu Shinto as it was heavily influenced by esoteric Tendai practices. These traditions were published in the mid to late seventeenth century by followers of Tenkai and are compiled in the Jigen Daishi Zenshū.

Reference: Kan'eiji, ed.. Jigen Daishi Zenshū. Edited by Kan'eiji. Vol. 1. Tokyo: Hensha hakkō, 1916.

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– No

↳ Are the scriptures alterable:

– No

Notes: There is near total uniformity in all the extant Engi. The one exception is in the Kishū Tōshōgū Engi which adds a final scroll that adds to the original by describing the founding of Kishū Tōshō Shrine and its attendant festivals.

↳ Are there formal institutions (i.e. institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders) for interpreting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a select group of people trained in transmitting the scriptures:

– No

↳ Is there a codified canon of scriptures:

– No

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There was great variation between the hundreds of Tōshō shrines that were the centers of Sannō Ichijitsu Shinto. The central shrine in Nikkō is a sprawling complex, but like many of the larger shrines, is not in an urban setting. Conversely, castle towns could often have very tiny shrines or even simple private altars.

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 220000

Notes: Nikkō Tōshōgū is 220,000 square meters and includes numerous buildings that are ornately decorated, sprawling gardens, and tree-lined avenues.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 36

Notes: The tallest structure at the Nikko Toshogu Shrine is the Five-Story Pagoda, which stands at about 36 meters (approximately 118 feet) tall. This pagoda, like many traditional Japanese pagodas, is both architecturally significant and beautifully decorated, adding to the grandeur of the shrine complex.

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– I don't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Notes: The central shrine in Nikkō was built surrounding the tomb of Ieyasu. His earlier tomb on Kunōzan in Shizuoka Prefecture remains the center of the Tōshōgū there. Furthermore, the second and third Tokugawa Shoguns, Tokugawa Hidetada (1579-1632), and Tokugawa Iemitsu (1604-1651) each had their own shrines built similarly and following Sannō Ichijitsu Shinto rites to deify themselves. Hidetada's grand mausoleum was called Taitoku-in and was in Edo before being destroyed in the Allied bombings during the War of Pacific Aggression. Iemitsu chose to have his grand mausoleum built directly adjacent to his grandfather's in Nikkō, where they both still stand today.

↳ Cemeteries:

– No

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Notes: While the Tōshō Shrines are today associated with the Shinto faith, they were generally temple-shrine complexes. The majority of the shrines' buildings and architecture followed Shinto traditions but the complexes were administered by a temple that was usually on the compound grounds. This administrative temple was called the honjidō (本池堂). The arrangement mirrored Sannō Ichijitsu Shinto's syncretic nature.

↳ Altars:

– Yes

Notes: Altars are common within Shinto ritual spaces such as shrines.

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

Notes: Devotional markers were selectively given out to high-ranking bushi in the form of charms containing prayers. These fuda (札) could be displayed as ornaments but were usually kept hidden away. Some other symbols came to be associated with Tōshō Daigongen such as the Tokugawa clan's mon (crest), the mitsuaioimon (triple hollyhock crest). This symbol was only used by the most powerful of the Tokugawa.

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Notes: The sacred spaces surrounding Tōshō Shrines were carefully restricted. However, the precise demarkations shifted over time, generally trending towards an opening of previously more exclusive areas. For example, at the Nikkō Tōshōgū Shrine, commoners were not allowed to pass the Ōgeba (大下馬), a stone or wooden marker that indicated where worshipers should dismount out of respect. They would therefore congregate before the Ōgeba. Those allowed beyond this point could congregate in one of the several courtyards leading to the Yōmeimon gate. Entry past this gate was restricted to the highest ranking warriors such as the shogun.

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Stone lanterns called tōrō (灯籠) were often gifted to Tōshōgū shrines by daimyo to show fealty and project wealth.

Is iconography present:

– Yes

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– Only religious public space

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: Dragons and baku (狛) are common motifs carved in relief on the walls, pillars, and ceilings of Tōshō Shrine buildings.

↳ Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

Notes: Tōshō Daigongen was depicted in portraits and statues and showed Ieyasu as he was later in life.

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– No

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– No

Notes: Prayers in the Sannō Ichijitsu Shinto are generally focused on real-world benefits. Peace, stability, and continuing success of the Tokugawa are the most frequent subjects of prayers in extant documents. Because of this, the afterlife does not appear to be a focus of Sannō Ichijitsu Shinto.

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– No

↳ Humans:

– No

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Field doesn't know

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to environmental features:

"Environmental features" refers to features in the landscape, mountains, rivers, cardinal directions etc...

– Yes

Notes: Almost all shrines venerating Tōshō Daigongen are located on mountaintops or hilltops. However, this is not a unique phenomenon in Shinto, as mountains are viewed as liminal spaces and are thus thought to be inherently sacred.

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: There were at least 19 shogunal pilgrimages between 1617 and 1843. These were grand affairs comprised of hundreds of retainers and even more attendants. Korean envoys were also forced to travel to Nikkō in a blizzard on at least one occasion in 1636.

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer "no" only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Field doesn't know

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Notes: Practitioners of the Sannō Ichijitsu Shinto faith were also members of other Buddhist sects and these other coincident religious practices would have played a much more significant role in shaping understandings of the afterlife.

Reincarnation in this world:

– Field doesn't know

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– No

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Are grave goods present:

– Field doesn't know

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Notes: The primary focus of worship in Sannō Ichijitsu Shinto was the Tōshō Daigongen. In Nankōbō Tenkai's formulation, Tokugawa Ieyasu's gongen was not only part of a kami triad (Tōshō Daigongen, Sannō Gongen, and Matarajin) but as each kami was thought to be the expedient incarnation of a Buddha, worship of the Sannō Ichijitsu Shinto kami triad was one in the same as worshipping the Buddha of healing (Yakushi Nyōrai), the Buddha of salvation (Amida Nyōrai) and the historical Buddha (Shaka Nyōrai). However, there is no documentary evidence that the adherents of Sannō Ichijitsu Shinto had any interest in these other deities, and instead focused on Tōshō Daigongen as the divinity of Tokugawa Ieyasu.

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– No

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– I don't know

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

- ↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:
 - I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
 - I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):
 - I don't know
- ↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):
 - Field doesn't know
- ↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:
 - No
- ↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:
 - Yes
- ↳ Human spirits can reward:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits can punish:

– I don't know

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– I don't know

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– No

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

↳ Power of beings is domain specific:

– Yes

↳ Other organization for pantheon:

– Yes [specify]: present, past, future

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– No

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Field doesn't know

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Is an eschatology present:

– No

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– No

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Notes: Although most engagement by adherents of Sannō Ichijitsu Shinto was voluntary, occasional participation in rituals and pilgrimages to Tōshō shrines or alters could be required by vassals when a lord (such as the shogun) was participating. Festivals were another time when vassals would be called upon to either participate in processions or serve as constables.

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Shogunal pilgrimages are an example of large-scale ritual participation and could comprise hundreds of adherents.

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Notes: Large-scale pilgrimages were irregular. There were at least 19 between 1617 and 1843.

Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– No

Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– No

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– No

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Field doesn't know

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– No

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– No

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The history of famine and famine relief in early modern Japan is long and complex. Various organizations from the Tokugawa bakufu to village councils could provide relief at different times based on factors such as scarcity, relations, and need.

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– No

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– No

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– No

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an an

institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– Yes

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– I don't know

Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

- ↳ Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:
– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Bibliography

Entry/Answer References

Reference: Yes, Kan'eiji, ed.. Jigen Daishi Zenshū. Edited by Kan'eiji. Vol. 1. Tokyo: Hensha hakkō, 1916.